

*Mariana Baloşescu
Faculty of Letters and Communication Sciences
Ştefan cel Mare University of Suceava
13 Universităţii Street, 720229
Suceava, Romania
e-mail: mariana_boca_ro@yahoo.com

*Porfirie Pescaru
Justinian Patriarch Faculty of Orthodox Theology
University of Bucharest
2-4 Sfânta Ecaterina Street, 040155
Bucharest, Romania
e-mail: pescarunicolae1@gmail.com

THE QUESTION OF THE IDEAL IN THE ARTS

Abstract

To talk about the ideal is an action as daring as necessary in our world. Through the ideological-social discourse, legitimized and nourished by the discourse of sciences and philosophy, the current man is led towards a definitive alienation from his natural need for an ideal. The teachings about the inherited ideal are also quickly abandoned. On the other hand, art reflects realities and often anticipates them. In this essay study, we would like to show that a simple analytical overview, from a few sequences, on the backbone of the representation of the ideal in artistic thinking, seen in its historical consanguinity with philosophical and theological thinking, reveals to us an unsettling dynamic of the vision of the ideal. Modern philosophical consciousness, especially after Kant and then after Nietzsche, and the ideologies it generated change so much the original figure of the ideal that today it becomes unrecognizable. Man is led outside his own nature, but also outside the memory of the historical civilizations he built. The perception that the writer, the artist, but also the philosopher conveys, especially after 1850, is that of the loss of the ideal. Unsurprisingly, from this negative energy a whole culture of the crisis of modernity has been produced, which, without treating the causes of the crisis, amplifies the crisis, justifies it and gives it, especially in the 20th century, an expansion that today breaks western societies from the models claimed civilizations: the Christian-Judaic model and the Greco-Latin model. The center of this culture of crisis, assumed as a permanent state in the postmodern world, is the very crisis of the ideal and the crisis of the ideal. It summarizes the tectonic mutations that the inner being goes through in the world in which we live. The question that arises is natural: what comes next? Can we identify reactions that art, philosophy and theology offer in this state of crisis of consciousness? There are working hypotheses and there are clearly formulated solutions, which we can by no means evoke in detail here. What we aim to do is point to some more significant fragments from a very broad debate. And, finally, the analysis sends the reader to the spiritual and discursive presence of the solutions out of the crisis of the ideal, in the (apparently) anarchic combustion of our strictly current culture.

* Mariana Baloşescu is a researcher in the field of modern culture and classical literature. She teaches comparative literature and the analysis of mentalities at the Ştefan cel Mare University of Suceava (Romania). She published under the name Mariana Boca books and studies of aesthetic and cultural interpretation: *Modernism between Literature and Philosophy* (2002); *European Mentalities* (2006); *Romanian Literature in the 20th century: the machine of the modernism and the histories of identity* (2007); *Memory and Precarity* (2019); *The memory of the texts and the canonical narrative* (2019); *Stories about the inner man* (2020), etc.

* Porfirie Pescaru is a theologian specialized in the area of the patristic thought and in the Philokalia Greek texts. His research is dedicated to the biblical memory and to the interpretation of the Orthodox Christian spirituality and Byzantine culture. He is affiliated to the Justinian Patriarch Faculty of Orthodox Theology of the University of Bucharest. He works for the Archdiocese of Suceava and Rădăuţi (The Orthodox Church of Romania).

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1. Introduction

To talk about the ideal is an action as daring as necessary in our world. Through the ideological-social discourse, legitimized and nourished by the discourse of sciences and philosophy, the current man is led towards a definitive alienation from his natural need for an ideal. The teachings about the inherited ideal are also quickly abandoned. On the other hand, art reflects realities and often anticipates them. In this essay study, we would like to show that a simple analytical overview, from a few sequences, on the backbone of the representation of the ideal in artistic thinking, seen in its historical consanguinity with philosophical and theological thinking, reveals to us an unsettling dynamic of the vision of the ideal. Modern philosophical consciousness, especially after Kant and then after Nietzsche, and the ideologies it generated change so much the original figure of the ideal that today it becomes unrecognizable. Man is led outside his own nature, but also outside the memory of the historical civilizations he built. The perception that the writer, the artist, but also the philosopher conveys, especially after 1850, is that of the loss of the ideal.

Unsurprisingly, from this negative energy a whole culture of the crisis of modernity has been produced, which, without treating the causes of the crisis, amplifies the crisis, justifies it and gives it, especially in the 20th century, an expansion that today breaks western societies from the models claimed civilizations: the Christian-Judaic model and the Greco-Latin model. The center of this culture of crisis, assumed as a permanent state in the postmodern world, is the very crisis of the ideal and the crisis of the ideal. It summarizes the tectonic mutations that the inner being goes through in the world in which we live.

The question that arises is natural: what comes next? Can we identify reactions that art, philosophy and theology offer in this state of crisis of consciousness? There are working hypotheses and there are clearly formulated solutions, which we can by no means evoke in detail here. What we aim to do is point to some more significant fragments from a very broad debate. And, finally, the analysis sends the reader to the spiritual and discursive presence of the solutions out of the crisis of the ideal, in the (apparently) anarchic combustion of our strictly current culture.

But how could we define the ideal and why is it worth talking about? The ideal is the most sensitive, the most subtle and the most influential part of human existence, in all its guises. Without exaggerating, we could say, therefore, that man, as a person with conscience and discernment, cannot exist outside of affirming an ideal. Even the loss of the ideal still shows a form of its presence - a search, an active or latent nostalgia for the ideal. In a very common perception, the ideal is the target towards which the human spirit tends in search of perfection, while recognizing it as either close or inaccessible. The ideal would be above all moral perfection - dreamed of, but never fully conquered. A principle or value pursued as an ethical goal. However, although the ideal is most easily identified through the moral virtues, it is in no way confused with them. It sums them up in the much more difficult to define power to understand and follow, the sages of the old cultures convey to us, but especially in love. The love of creation for the Creator, say the kings of Israel, David and Solomon, in the Old Testament. Man's love for God and man's love for man, say the authors of the Gospels and the Christian Apostles - Christ's witnesses. The ideal would be the good, the eternal truth, from which beauty and universal harmony are born, say the Greek and Latin thinkers, because the spirit of the real person is attracted to the ideal, in the natural nostalgia of man subject to time and history, for perfection.

The ideal, however, has no justification other than belief in its existence. The trust of man from the ancient worlds in the presence of the ideal beyond time and history, gives him absolute uniqueness. And King Solomon, and Homer or Sophocles, Socrates and Saint Paul, Plato and Blessed Augustine, Virgilius or Marcus Aurelius - therefore, Jewish thinkers, Greek poets and philosophers, Roman poets and thinkers, the Fathers of the Christian Church, all together testify to the uniqueness of the ideal, as singular and indivisible divine value. At the same time, the consciousness of the real man, when he approaches his ideal, lends him the signs of his personal knowledge. The fruit of experiences and the power of the real man to understand things, personal knowledge is unrepeatable in its internal logic and thus acquires another type of uniqueness. It represents the primary legitimacy of the arts.

Once the ideal is revealed to the consciousness of the real man, from the personal knowledge it generates, that divine energy irreducible to the person cannot be missing. From that subtly transfiguring encounter, the perfect man is born, as the historical face of the eternal Creator. In this vision, the path to the ideal is only internal. On the other hand, the ideal is not an inner good of the person, but of Divinity, of God, says Socrates, in the Defense... recorded by Plato. The ideal is revealed only in the inner experience shaped by the personal consciousness, at the meeting between the mind and the heart. The ideal, as a principle but a divine value, is embodied, therefore, unseen in the unseen space of the person's interiority. The content of the representations of the ideal is directly dependent on the consciousness of the person who evokes it and who calls it. And the way of consciousness towards the ideal is born from the freedom of the inner man to give meaning to the good and from his discernment or sobriety (Gr. *nepsis*), in the philological sense, with which he builds and follows his limits in the face of the presence of evil. Christian thinkers show that the eyes of the mind and heart, through humble contemplation, can lead the inner man to perfection.

2. The position of the artist towards the ideal

But dreaming, contemplation, meditation, prayer - which give energy to the creator of poetry, ideas, music, stories - multiply and complicate the representations of the ideal, in a dynamic that is difficult to predict, as in a never-ending mental dance of the approach and distance from the intended target. And art in all its manifestations, especially the story and the poem, becomes a prophecy of the evolution of the soul precisely because the artist pursues, intuitively or determinedly, the reflection of the ideal and the positioning in relation to its nature. Art as prophecy is more than simple anticipation, because anticipation is implicitly accompanied by its moral criticism. Therefore, the ideal, as an inner reality, receives very different content and faces, in the interpretation of thinkers, artists, theologians, poets, philosophers, writers, mystical spirits and lay people. Then, the approach or distance from the ideal, as an inner reality, expresses in the history of arts and thought the vision of the art creator on man and, above all, on human consciousness. From Solomon, Homer, Socrates and Sophocles, to Kant, Gogol, Flaubert or Nietzsche, from King David's Psalms, Socrates' Defense and Plato's Dialogues, Greek art, to Dante's Divine Comedy, medieval art and philosophy, Byzantine culture, then Shakespeare's Hamlet or Miguel de Cervantes' Don Quixote, from the Epistles of Saint Paul, De Magister, of Blessed Augustine, the thought of the Fathers of the Christian Church and the philological writings, going towards the art of the Renaissance, the philosophy of the Enlightenment, the novel of the century 19th century, nihilistic thought and (post)modernist literature of the 20th century, up to the posthuman ideology of the current century, there is a vertebral dynamic of the conceptualization and revelation of the ideal, which shows the ultimate identity given to man not only by every creator of art and philosophy, but also by the dominant groups in the society in which it manifests itself.

3. The ideal in ancient art and thought

The ideal represents for many thinkers and artists of the ancient worlds an absolute reality of the heart, revealed to the consciousness of the person who knows himself to be part of God's consciousness. From this perspective, the ideal has a strong content, because it is supported by a knowing consciousness, capable of generating certainty, value, trust, inner balance. Socrates (470 - 399 BC), Plato's master and father of wisdom in the Western canonical culture, "knows that he knows nothing" and that "only God is wise". He is the one who speaks to the current European about the man inside the man. And he asks his Athenians to concern themselves only with the soul, in order to acquire virtue, because those who ignore the investigation of what is good, true and beautiful deserve to be called slaves, in his conception, according to the testimony of Xenophon, his disciple (Xenophon: 3-4). For Socrates, life has meaning only if it is devoted to the ideal that was hardly revealed by God, after much research. He thus addressed the Athenians who judged him for the corruption of the young, for the belief in a single God and for the morality of inner virtues:

...I have for being 'wise'-because those present on each occasion imagine me to 'be wise regarding the matters on which I examine others. But in fact, gentlemen, it would appear that it

is only the god who is truly wise; and that he is saying to us, through this oracle, that human wisdom is worth little or nothing. It seems that when he says 'Socrates', he makes use of my name, merely taking me as an example-as if to say, 'The wisest amongst you, human beings, is anyone like Socrates who has recognized that with respect to wisdom he is truly worthless.' That is why, even to this day, I still go about seeking out and searching into anyone I believe to be wise, citizen or foreigner, in obedience to the god. Then, as soon as I find that someone is not wise, I assist the god by proving that he is not. Because of this occupation, I have had no time at all for any activity to speak of, either in public affairs or in my family life; indeed, because of my service to the god, I live in extreme poverty. (*Apology of Socrates*: 1983, 23 a, b)

Then, Socrates explains meticulously and head-on what content should be given to the ideal, how it should be pursued and what is its importance in the life of every human being. His words speak for themselves and summarize the deep memory of the Western European on the content attributed to the ideal:

I have the greatest fondness and affection for you, fellow Athenians, but I will obey my god rather than you; and so long as I draw breath and am able, shall never give up practising philosophy, or exhorting and showing the way to any of you whom I ever encounter, by giving my usual sort of message. "Excellent friend," I shall say; "You are an Athenian. Your city is the most important and renowned for its wisdom and power; so are you not ashamed that, while you take care to acquire as much wealth as possible, with honour and glory as well, yet you take no care or thought for understanding or truth, or for the best possible state of your soul?" "And should any of you dispute that, and claim that he does take such care, I will not let him go straight away nor leave him, but I will question and examine and put him to the test; and if I do not think he has acquired goodness, though he says he has, I shall say, "Shame on you, for setting the lowest value upon the most precious things, and for rating inferior ones more highly!" That I shall do for anyone I encounter, young or old, alien or fellow citizen; but all the more for the latter, since your kinship with me is closer. (*Apology of Socrates*: 1983, 29 d, e; 30 a)

But, long before Socrates, King Solomon (971-931 BC) states that the ideal means overcoming ignorance and the falsity of any wisdom taken from anything other than the connection of the soul with its Creator:

For God giveth to a man that is good in his
sight wisdom, and knowledge, and joy: but to the
sinner he giveth travail, to gather and to heap up,
that he may give to him that is good before God.
This also is vanity and vexation of spirit. (*Ecclesiastes* 1976, 2: 26)

He uses the awareness and verbalization of vanity not to bring his own spirit and the spirit of the one listening to him to despair, but to affirm, like Socrates a few centuries later, that no knowledge allowed to man can encompass the mysteries of God. Solomon's skepticism with tragic fibers makes faith in God the ideal that heals the consciousness of the painful discovery of the futility of all forms of reality and the entire human effort to go through them. True wisdom means precisely the assumption of man's ignorance. Beyond any experience, the knowledge acquired by man through his own research is relative, often deceptive and even useless. The only certainty, the sure truth lies in the permanent proximity to God and in the trust that true life is beyond death. The relationship between Solomon's vision of the ideal and that of Socrates is extremely vivid:

I communed with mine own heart, saying, Lo, I am come to great estate, and
have gotten more wisdom than all they that have
been before me in Jerusalem: yea, my heart had
great experience of wisdom and knowledge.
And I gave my heart to know wisdom, and to
know madness and folly: I perceived that this
also is vexation of spirit. For in much wisdom
is much grief: and he that increaseth knowledge, increaseth sorrow. (*Ecclesiastes* 1976 1: 16-18)

The purpose of the Ecclesiastes is to exercise his mission as a master and to give his disciples the solution to the exit from the anarchy towards which the oppressive feeling of vanity pushes the human mind. Ecclesiastes heals the consciousness of the reader and his disciple from fear and sadness. Solomon's ideal is the acquisition of that wisdom which is nourished by fear and shyness before God. Thus, the source of happiness is in the teaching not subject to precariousness that gives man the ideal of discovering and obeying God. In his text, Solomon bequeaths a philosophical and mystical awareness of the ideal, which will generate and shape the creative consciousness of art:

Or ever the silver cord be loosed, or the golden bowl be broken, or the pitcher be broken at the fountain, or the wheel broken at the cistern. Then shall the dust return to the earth as it was: and the spirit shall return unto God who gave it. Vanity of vanities, saith the preacher; all is vanity. [...]...The words of the wise are as goads, and as nails fastened by the masters of assemblies, which are given from one shepherd. And further, by these, my son, be admonished: of making many books there is no end; and much study is a weariness of the flesh. Let us hear the conclusion of the whole matter: Fear God, and keep his commandments: for this is the whole duty of man. For God shall bring every work into judgment, with every secret thing, whether it be good, or whether it be evil. (*Ecclesiastes* 12: 6-8; 11-14).

Homer, especially in the *Odyssey*, is very close to the Ecclesiastes' perspective on man. Most likely, Homer did not know Solomon's text, therefore the similarities as well as the differences between their spiritual visions are very telling for the core values of their cultural models - the Jewish cultural model and the Homeric Greek cultural model. The most significant moment in Homer's *Odyssey* is when Odysseus meets Demodocus on the island of the Phaeacians, at the court of King Alcinous. The blind singer is an *alter-ego* of Homer and a prototype of the artist's consciousness, in which, however, the mystical consciousness and the philosophical revelation speak. Odysseus discovers that Demodocus, who, being blind, had not gone through his exceptional experiences, knew much better than himself everything he had experienced and understood the meaning of existence. Demodocus' knowing conscience is a "*divine gift*", as Odysseus himself calls it.

Homer thus shows that the ideal of the man of his world should not be the acquisition of wisdom from experience, but the soul's proximity to Divinity. Saint Paul, the authors of the Gospels, the Fathers of the Christian Church, the authors of the texts of the Greek Philokalia show that the ideal is the *deified man* or the perfect man. He can only be reached through a permanent Christ consciousness, through *Imitatio Christi*, says Blessed Augustine, because Christ is the only Master (*De Magister*). And Marcus Aurelius, the Roman emperor who certainly knew Christian teaching and Greek philosophy, formulates the ideal in Greek, but in a Christian spirit:

...I ... understood that the nature of good is moral beauty and that of evil is moral ugliness and that the nature of the one who errs is related to me, not only by his blood and seed, but also by reason and participation in divine...[...] ... no one can morally hate me, and I cannot be angry with someone related to me, nor can I hate him. For we were born to help each other, like the feet, the hands, the eyelids, the upper and lower rows of teeth. Therefore, to act against one another is against nature, and to detest one's fellow man is to treat him as an adversary. (Marcus Aurelius: 2022, 25-26).

In the pre-modern world, in ancient cultures and in those of the Christian Middle Ages, the thinker and the artist seek the perfection of man by approaching the ideal reality, which is always immaterial, belongs to the divine order and reveals itself internally, in an unseen plane of things. Thus, ancient art and philosophy are placed in the horizon of something other than their own discourse, their own territory. They open to something infinitely higher than art or philosophy itself. The artist does not create for himself. His work is dedicated to approaching that ideal horizon, with the aim of leading both his mind and that of the other (the reader, the viewer) towards the vision of what the inner being can perfect.

The art of Antiquity is deeply cathartic. The reflected consciousness is a personal one, but it goes transpersonal, through cathartic energy. Personal consciousness is freed from its precarious nature through revealed belonging. The discovery and affirmation of belonging give content and

representation to the ideal, in artistic and philosophical thinking. Personal consciousness is part of God's consciousness. For the Greeks, consciousness participates in divine knowledge (Homer, Socrates, Plato). Of course, the overcoming of precariousness, the search for the ideal takes place in Solomon's consciousness in a different way from that of Homer, but also in a similar way. Overcoming precarity happens in very different degrees and postures, in different discourses, languages and forms, for thinkers and artists. Beyond the marked differences, there remains the dominant positioning, which unites all these visions: the understanding of the person's consciousness as part of the consciousness of the Divinity.

Art and thought before modernity and that which is different from modern art and thought, seeks to overcome particularity by revealing the eternal reality, it is not confused with the particular thing. At the same time, it is personal, in the sense that only the human person partakes of the divine Person - God the Father, God the Son, God the Holy Spirit - and the truth of the eternal suprapersonal reality. From this transhistorical perspective, there is an art and a thinking beyond modernity and which, at the same time, subordinates modernity as a marginal territory. Its original cultural model - the *pattern* - is universal, and its legitimation comes from the inherent nature of human consciousness, which can only live for an ideal that includes and surpasses it.

4. The ideal in modern world

The artist of the new worlds, called *modern* after the Renaissance, together with the *modern* philosopher, passionately ventures into approximating the ideal and multiplies it subversively, forcing the abandonment of the old belief in the uniqueness and singularity of its ultimate nature. The artists and philosophers of modernity give the ideal multiple visible forms - in the sense of figures or expressions accessible to alterity, through word, sound, color, matter. In this way, the artist after Dante Alighieri and starting with him exposes the ideal of problematization, mystification, destructuring - blasphemy and revolt, love and indifference. It petrifies him on sight, generating all the acts of flattery and rejection that the human being is capable of. This is why the modern artist, together with the modern philosopher, participates not only in the re-knowing of the ideal, but also in its re-invention, through the so-called adaptation to the historical being of man. And re-inventing the ideal, updating it, means, in fact, confiscating its moral core and the original spirituality that gives it legitimacy. It means its successive compromise, transformation, re-formulation, until its ultimate expression can acquire meanings in which the original pattern of the ideal - that divine horizon of faith, love and moral perfection - becomes impossible to recognize, because it is completely expelled from the invented content by the (im)moral imagination of the artist and the thinker. The civilizational paradox of modernity is that the unrestrained moral imagination of the modern artist liquidates both the morality of his world and the energy of the search for the ideal as an inner reality.

For the thinkers and artists of modern worlds, the ideal perceptible to the spirit becomes a transformable mental reality, a projection of the intellect, or simply a fiction. The ideal seen as a fictional creation ends up, by way of consequence, very weak in its content. He only appears as a (very) distant copy of a superhuman reality, to which approach would be, in fact, impossible. In the *Canon of Pure Reason*, Kant says:

It is humiliating for human reason that in its pure use it achieves nothing, it even needs a discipline, to curb its excesses and to prevent the illusions that come from it...[...][human reason] suspects objects that are of great interest to it. He steps on the path of mere speculation, in order to approach them; but they flee from her. Probably, one can hope for more success on the only road that remains, that of practical use. (Kant, 1885: 567-568).

Kant recognizes, like Solomon and Socrates, man's impotence and his limits. But, instead of getting closer to the real, he definitively moves away from God and turns to his precarious reason, to look for all the energy of the ideal there. In order to be able to support this movement, it will prepare the transfer of the content given to the ideal in externalities, in social and in matter. The inner reality is, in fact, abandoned. In its place is put a substitute that imitates and usurps it: the psychological man, with his imponderable materiality:

Human reason, in a kind of its knowledge, has the peculiar fate of being overwhelmed by questions that it cannot avoid, because they are imposed on it by the nature of reason itself, but which it cannot answer, because they exceed the entire capacity of human reason. (Kant, 1985: 21).

What does modernity actually mean? The modern man is only developing his own (peripheral) pattern of thinking - modernity in its multiple faces. By detachment, opposition, ambiguity, destructuring, denial, conflicting reporting, etc. in relation to the spiritual and cultural heritage, from which it continuously feeds, the modern consciousness of the artist and the philosopher re-writes it, re-interprets it, distorts it, profanes it. Imagining that it is freeing itself from the inherited memory, the modern consciousness cannot break away from it for a moment, despite the abyss created by the languages of philosophers and poets, writers, (post)modern artists. In modern art and thought, the creator privileges particularity, turns his back on ideal reality and creates that art for art's sake, art for art's sake, which no longer recognizes either the existence or the necessity of an ideal horizon to motivate and overcome it. Consciousness definitively returns to itself. He distances himself from the Divinity, then simply denies the existence of God and divine morality. It rejects the Christian memory, the Jewish memory, reformulates the Greek and the Latin memory. By building a culture of man – the *humanism*, it legitimizes only the personal self, which, in fact, is massively loaded with the psychological self.

The artistic and philosophical humanism internalizes the ideal. The ideal effectively becomes internal good, good of interiority. And the psychological self has at least a hybrid identity. It appears as a zone of transfer and protoplasmic communication between body and soul, mind and heart, so between the materiality and immateriality of the person. Modern art progressively becomes, from the Renaissance, through the realisms of the 19th and 20th centuries, a non-cathartic and then profoundly anti-cathartic art. The reality evoked is mainly psychological and social. It breaks into fragments, in an open, unfinished puzzle, scattered in endless instants, sequences, emotions, states, experiences. A puzzle impossible to put together, impossible to close, so that both the performer and its creator can have the satisfaction of understanding the meaning hidden in his drawing. Modernist poets and novelists fully evoke this state of crisis, where the ideal is fully replaced by the ghosts and demonism of psychism. Let us listen to T. S. Eliot, in *The Waste Land*:

April is the cruellest month, breeding
Lilacs out of the dead land, mixing
Memory and desire, stirring
Dull roots with spring rain.
Winter kept us warm, covering
Earth in forgetful snow, feeding
A little life with dried tubers.
Summer surprised us, coming over the Starnbergersee
With a shower of rain; we stopped in the colonnade,
And went on in sunlight, into the Hofgarten,
And drank coffee, and talked for an hour.
Bin gar keine Russin, stamm' aus Litauen, echt deutsch.
And when we were children, staying at the archduke's,
My cousin's, he took me out on a sled,
And I was frightened. He said, Marie,
Marie, hold on tight. And down we went.
In the mountains, there you feel free.
I read, much of the night, and go south in the winter. (Eliot, 1982: 41)

Consciousness fully experiences its vulnerability. She calls herself precarious and doesn't want to be otherwise. It rapidly evolves towards nihilism, where the vehemence of the languages of Nietzsche, Cioran, Derrida, etc. cynically denies the possibility of human perfection. Humanism fails in nihilism and gives rise to posthumanist demonism. The new postmodern consciousness does not only deny the Divinity. The man also denies. Denies membership of any kind. Posthumanism is also a

high-risk ideological-artistic fiction. Man imagines through hyper-realistic stories and theses how he creates his own replacement with the machine. Through the most abrupt denial of memory, the consciousness of the current man who self-identifies as *post-human*, therefore - *non-human* and/or *anti-human*, invents a Luciferian type of *non-belonging*. Her nuclear identity representation is a suicidal contradiction. Man belongs to the machine, and not the other way around. A critical anticipation of great subtlety leaves in E. M. Forster in *The machine stops* (1909).

The aesthetic man. Therefore, modernity, in its fulminant dynamics, has at least three major ages. The artists, philosophers and writers of the 17th - 18th centuries, creators of the first modernity, humanist - revolutionary and optimistic, bring a transcendental vision on the beauty created by art. They affirm art itself as the horizon of perfection, as a space where man perfects himself, as a world where the purity of the ideal is reached. In this aesthetic and philosophical discourse, the ideal tends to be confused with art itself and emerges from the inner - spiritual reality. The ideal migrates towards a simultaneously inner and outer reality. A hybrid reality already, semi-materialized, even if this process takes place in the i-material materiality of the story, the image, the sound.

The consciousness of the creative person already turns to himself and identifies in (self) projection the ideal of art. And the fictions of multiple (self) projections take the place of the perfect Christian man. The horizon beyond man is deserted. Man imagines himself perfect in himself, through himself.

The known relationships between good, truth and beauty are turned upside down. The beautiful (artistic) generates and legitimizes the good and the truth. That is why Renaissance and Classicist art still produce the illusion of identification with the ideal, seen as pure aesthetic gratuity or as aesthetic emotion (Toma Pavel, *The Art of Removal*). The perfect man is diluted to the point of disappearance in the aesthetic man. The person's consciousness (self) illusions itself to be knowledgeable, like Cervantes's Don Quixote. Roger Scruton, a British conservative philosopher, therefore proposes the return, at least contemplatively, to the art of the first modernity, as a solution to save the link between the person and the ideal. Although Roger Scuton's idea has its seduction, it represents a false solution and is a pathetic reaction, a form of dramatic nostalgia, without any philosophical and spiritual credibility, without even aesthetic consequences.

The second modernity, starting especially after 1850, is the (self) critical and pessimistic one. The perception of the ideal is internalized, which is no longer conceived as a divine horizon, a superhuman plane. Internalization means psychologizing. The perfect man sought by the ancients first becomes a man blinded by psychological terror, then simply annihilated by nihilism. The ideal becomes non-ideal and anti-ideal. The great writers of the 19th century - Gogol, Flaubert, Dostoevsky, even Tolstoy - clearly see and reflect the direction. The visionaries Shakespeare and Cervantes anticipate the failure of this consciousness and of modernity itself. Shakespeare shows that the truth reflected in the play orchestrated by Hamlet himself has the gift of causing disaster: madness, death. Intended by the creator Hamlet to order the imperfect garden, the mad gardener's art leads the world and reality into anarchy, death, disorder. Art cannot order the cosmos, but deceives the personal conscience, drives the soul into madness, says Shakespeare from behind the curtain.

Similarly, Cervantes, through Don Quixote and his dream of the world as ideal beauty, allegorically demonstrates that man does not have the inner energy to nurture such an illusion. What he will succeed in is deceiving others. The projection of Don Quixote taken to Sancho Panza's mind becomes a copy of the illusion that fully relativizes the content and nature of the ideal in the sailing interpretation of the moderns.

We cannot extend the analysis here. The last age of modernity is the strictly current one, attributed to the so-called *posthuman* man, who leaves humanism, the aesthetic man and the psychological man. The posthumanist ideal is the improvement of the corporeal man, through the machine also created by man. Posthumanism, with its variant called transhumanism, brings an absolute distortion of the ideal and of consciousness. The ideal as an inner reality is progressively transferred into corporeality, materiality and exteriority, throughout the history of modernity, and suddenly becomes a purely external reality in the experiments of the current posthumanists. Man renounces himself and manufactures a primitive pseudo-ideal.

5. Closing thoughts

As I have already shown, the solution proposed by Western conservative philosophy, through the very influential voice of Roger Scruton, namely the rediscovery of classical beauty as a source of the ideal, cannot produce any kind of revival of it. Anca Vasiliu, declared philosopher of the year 2022 in France, has a critical position towards transhumanism in a recent interview:

Culturally speaking, transhumanism is a consequence of nihilism, rooted in a certain modernity, that of the 19th century, whose consequences produced the disasters of the 20th century and seem to fuel the disasters of the 21st century. But I think a slow process of decanting and getting out of nihilism has already begun. Appeals and more or less spectacular reversals are short-lived, like any storm. Being remains steadfast in its depth, and nature spontaneously recovers its creative capacities and is reborn even from the ashes. (Vasiliu, 2022: 1)

Confidence in the depth of being and in nature's ability to recover its energy does not lead to the rebirth of the ideal. Anca Vasiliu, when asked for a saving way out of transhumanism, strategically withdraws into methodical definitions, takes refuge in the analytical thinking of the *diaphanous*, of the historical connections between Greek philosophers and Christian thought, without asserting a strong conscience. Moreover, he recognizes the limits of the symbolic-discursive imaginary created by philosophers, from Socrates until today, and chooses to remain in his methodical territory, promoted not as truth, but as an exercise of the mind:

There is a "path" in philosophy: the term "method", *methodos*, means the path that leads you to accomplish something or to obtain a cognitive result. And of course, the problem of "truth" in philosophy is posed and demonstrated either as purely semantic truth, - a clear phrase necessarily states a truth - or as intelligible truth, reference that goes beyond the accidental to recover the essential. [...] But philosophy is not the Way, the Truth and the Life. It is a discipline of thought that helps us understand and talk about truths, the meanings of life, and the methodologies of knowledge. (Vasiliu, 2022: 1)

On the other hand, in Christian thinking, truth is not a matter of semantics or a problem of intelligibility. Truth is the core of wisdom and thus wisdom gives birth to both the search for the ideal and the hope in its existence:

My son, eat honey, for it is good, and the honeycomb, for it is sweet unto thy mouth. So shall the knowledge of wisdom be unto thy soul, if thou find it, and there shall be an end, and thine hope shall not be cut off. (*The Proverbs Solomon*, 24: 13, 14)

Ideal without wisdom does not exist, just as true wisdom is only that which knows the ideal. Boris Pasternak, in the novel *Doctor Zhivago*, reminds us that the Christian man, while living in history, is outside of it, because his ideal is only one: the salvation. Zhivago goes through all the terrible trials he goes through with tragic serenity because he knows the truth from childhood: human life is a journey towards the Kingdom of God. History, no matter how wild, is only a context, an accident. And the fragile being of man has to go through it ignoring it. He will have only one goal: not to lose sight, not to forget the ideal, but to live perfectly within the horizon of the ideal. For Zhivago, to acquire this wisdom is to acquire the whole world.

So that the man of our days can reborn in his heart the ideal - faith, hope and love, he must remember the teaching of Saint Paul, from the *First Epistle to the Corinthians*:

Guard against self-deception, each of you. If someone among you thinks he is wise in this age, let him become foolish so that he can become wise. (Saint Paul, 1987: 3, 18)

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